

Digital platforms of the gig economy: from matchmaking to boundary making

Roser Pujadas
LSE
r.pujadas@lse.ac.uk

Daniel Curto-Millet
Spanish National Research Council
(CSIC)
daniel.curto@cchs.csic.es

Abstract

The sharing economy is perceived as a source of empowerment for individuals who can easily participate in direct economic exchanges with each other (Botsman & Rogers, 2011), or less optimistically as an expression of economic neoliberalism (Srnicek, 2016) or “Reaganism by other means” (Scholz, 2016). It is commonly defined as a move towards access rather than ownership (Rifkin, 2001) in which digital platforms function as “matchmakers” (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016) of offer and demand. While digital platforms tend to be unproblematically presented as the technological infrastructure of the sharing economy, we argue that constituting the boundaries of infrastructures is political and performative, that is, it is implicated in ontological politics, with consequences in the distribution of responsibilities (Latour, 2003; Mol, 2013; Woolgar & Lezaun, 2013). We propose a diffractive reading (Haraway, 1992; Barad, 2007) of the digital platforms of the sharing economy to investigate the material-discursive production of digital platforms and their participation in the reconfiguring of the world (Barad 2007). Drawing on an empirical case study of Uber, including an analysis of court cases, we examine how the (in)visibility of infrastructure is mobilized (Larkin 2013). We argue that the representation of Uber as a “digital platform”, as “just the technological infrastructure” mediating car drivers and clients, is a political act that attempts to redefine social responsibilities, while black boxing important dimensions of the algorithmic infrastructure. We also show how some of these (in)visibilities become exposed in court, and some of the boundaries reshaped, with implications for the definition of objects, subjects and their responsibilities.

Key words

Digital infrastructures, digital platforms, sharing economy, gig economy, Uber

Introduction

The pervasiveness of digital infrastructures is transforming our daily practices, forms of knowledge production, and socioeconomic exchanges. It is changing the reach of interactions, and forms of coordination and organizing. The process of digitalization and digital convergence has blurred organizational and industrial boundaries (Tilson, Lyytinen, & Sørensen, 2010) and has given rise to a wide range of new business models and forms of value creation. Among them, digital platforms have facilitated the emergence of the so called collaborative or sharing economy.

Although the concept of sharing and the existence of informal peer-to-peer exchanges is nothing new, the new digital ecosystem has scaled up the phenomenon. However, the label is such, that contradictory notions of sharing co-exist embedded in very different socioeconomic models: from the commons based peer production exemplified by Wikipedia, to the Unicorn model of the gig economy supported by venture capital represented by Uber.

Despite the allure of the sharing economy, critical voices are raising concerns about various negative social effects related to the gig economy: erosion of worker's rights, issues of liability, unfair competition, to mention only some. In fact, Uber, or various Ubers, we should say, have faced several court cases or governmental regulations in various countries that have limited their attempts to be free of responsibilities towards workers. What we will show in this paper is how in Uber's attempt to promote a specific socioeconomic ordering, the mobilization of Uber as "just the technological infrastructure" mediating car drivers and clients, becomes a political act. Thus, the visualisation of the infrastructure as "just a technology", a "platform", is a categorizing moment (Larkin, 2013) that allows Uber to present itself as the benevolent neutral mediator of individuals providing services, and citizens in search for cheaper rides; hiding other fundamental aspects that sustain and characterise such infrastructure.

We will argue that the concept of digital infrastructure might allow us to theorise the sharing economy in ways that broaden the scope of current research on digital platforms in the Information Systems field.

Sharing in the collaborative economy

What's yours is mine and what's mine is my own

Old proverb

Sharing economy and associated terms such as gig economy, and collaborative economy, have been used to convey a change of paradigm taking place in the digital economic ecosystem in which peer-to-peer exchanges are facilitated by digital platforms. This change of paradigm that the sharing economy pre-supposes is deeply embedded within the dominant political economic thought which takes the view that innovation is a necessary component of progress (both as a system of production and a system of values) (e.g. Jaffe & Lerner, 2006; Schumpeter, 2009). As a result, innovation and anything that is related to it, is imbued with positive connotations. Some authors, suspicious of the unquestioned underlying positivity associated with innovation, have searched for the discourses behind the implementation of innovation (Godin, 2016), finding that, hidden behind the curtain were old accounts made new (Suchman & Bishop, 2000).

The notion of sharing economy is appealing, as sharing is associated to positive images of community building, the efficient use or reuse of limited resources in an environmentally fragile planet, and in which individuals are "empowered" to exchange resources with other individuals, as any service or underused resource can be easily matched with demand in ways previously unthinkable (Belk, 2007; Botsman & Rogers, 2011). However, the elasticity of the term is such, that differing notions of sharing economy co-exist: it has been posited as a new way of doing business and exchanging goods and services (Botsman & Rogers, 2011), sharing resources, and of co-producing goods, services and knowledge (Benkler, 2006; Scholz & Schneider, 2016). It has been associated both to the gift economy and the commons (Benkler, 2006; Ostrom, 1990), and to platform capitalism (Srnicsek, 2016), despite the gaping differences between these economic mechanisms.

The same label "sharing economy" has been equally applied to refer, for instance, to Freecycle—where people give away for free unneeded goods to whoever wants to collect them—, or to Uber—the best-known example of gig economy, in which a

corporation owns an app-based platform that matches drivers with consumers for a fee. It seems that it is to this second sort of model of privately owned platform that the term has come to be most frequently associated to. Recent reports on the "collaborative economy" commissioned by the European Commission (De Groen & Maselli, 2016), and on the "sharing economy" by Morgan Stanley, and by PwC, focus on ventures such as Uber, Upwork, Airbnb, and the way they are transforming our economies. Similarly, media and public discourse tends to associate sharing economy to successful for-profit ventures such as AirBnB and Uber, which are seen as disruptive innovators, seemingly, (and for some, ideally) beyond the control of traditional, legitimate players such as Taxi unions, the hospitality sector, and regulators.

Some pundits have taken an individualist view of the sharing economy, understood as liberation from traditional fetters that discourage economic flows. Sharing economy, in this perspective, is a source of empowerment for individuals who can easily participate in direct economic exchanges with each other (Botsman & Rogers, 2011). Notions of sharing economy that focus on dis-intermediation, however, seem to downplay the important role, and substantial benefits, of platform owners such as Uber or AirBnB. Conversely, authors such as Scholz (2016), Slee (2015), or Srnicek (2016) present a much more critical view towards these powerful platforms, noting their neoliberal and monopolistic drive, and reflecting on negative implications such as the erosion of worker's rights, issues of liability, or unfair competition, to mention some. As Scholz (2016, p. 6) puts it, the sharing economy is "Reaganism by other means", conveying the idea that the sharing economy is neither new nor "neutral" in the way sharing takes place.

In a society increasingly prone to crises of legitimation (Habermas, 2015), where societal problems can be of such a level that any single actor is incapable of resolving them on their own (Beck, 1992), businesses are increasingly viewed as those most capable to define the terms of such solutions (Schultz, Castelló, & Morsing, 2013). More often than not, the definition of these terms is based on black-boxed technology innovations which further pre-empts contestation. If we consider that the sharing economy is sufficiently elastic to mean a number of things and that these meanings and interpretations can be contradictory, then we need to

look inside the black-box that various actors are producing (Latour, 2005). These black-boxes will eventually hide the creation of certain realities and simplify certain phenomena so that they become “normalised”. If in fact there are many sharing economies, different materialisations, it is only by peering inside these black-boxes in the making that we can understand their reach and political ambition. By political ambition, we mean their capacity or intentions to arrange realities and actors along desired orders. We suggest that the creation of those black-boxes in the form of socially-embedded technology hold intentions that betray explicit or implicit competing views of how actors should relate with one another and influence the very nature and understanding of sharing taken by society. In trying to uncover these processes of ontological politics we will draw on the concept of digital infrastructure and its theorisation.

From digital platforms to infrastructuring the sharing economy

Digital platforms are seen to underlie the current development of the sharing and the gig economies, and of many other business models and forms of connectivity. Such transformations have resulted in a growing interest in the study of digital platforms within the information systems (IS) field. However, digital platforms remain undertheorized, and new research avenues are needed which adequately account for their sociotechnical nature (Reuver, Sørensen, & Basole, 2017). In this paper, we aim to contribute to open the black box of the digital platform, more specifically that of Uber, drawing on a concept with a longer tradition in information systems literature and science and technology studies (STS), that of infrastructure. In fact, some have suggested that digital platforms are a “less complex subtype of digital infrastructure with specific control arrangements.” (Hanseth & Lyytinen, 2010; Reuver et al., 2017)

From an engineering point view, digital platforms have been defined as layered modular systems, consisting of a core, complements and interfaces (Baldwin & Woodard, 2008; Yoo, Henfridsson, & Lyytinen, 2010b). The core (sometimes referred to as 'the platform') is characterised by its low variety and high reusability; complements, on the other hand, are components with high variety and low reusability. Such architecture, it has been argued, facilitates the addition or removal

of features, and thus, the evolvability of a product. While this characterisation could also be applied to a shopping mall, the digitality (Kallinikos, Aaltonen, & Marton, 2013) of digital platforms, has been associated to unparalleled generativity, scalability, flexibility, and evolvability (Tilson et al., 2010).

In the recent years, literature in the areas of information systems, business and management, have considered the important implications of such architecture for the development of new business models. From this vantage point, 'digital platform' becomes a techno-organizational concept that points at the highly dynamic environment of interrelated firms in the economic digital ecosystem (Gawer, 2014; Tiwana, Konsynski, & Bush, 2010; Yoo, Henfridsson, & Lyytinen, 2010a). A clear example of a digital platform is a smart phone, with its operating system and all its apps. An extremely evolvable and customisable "product", which results from the contribution of many different actors.

While the gig economy is sustained by digital platforms, we suggest that these approaches do not help unravel the many different "sharing economies" that digital platforms can help sustain, and do not shed light on important dimensions of the platform-based gig economy. Indeed, one could study Uber as a platform with a layered modular architecture, where for instance, maps or payment systems have become integrated. This, however, is not telling us much about other sort of orderings that Uber tries to sustain.

In the recent years several disciplines have turned their attention to the study of the sharing economy. In such literature digital platforms tend to be conceived not as modular architectures, but as "matchmakers" (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016) of offer and demand. These dominant conceptualisations of the digital platforms of the sharing economy are in consonance with the modernist view of infrastructures as the material substrates that support free circulation of goods and people, as an integral part of the market economy and the liberalist concept of progress (Foucault, 2010; Larkin, 2013; Mattelart, 2000).

Infrastructures are frequently perceived as the material substrates that enable other objects to operate (pipes, roads, wires, etc.). From this perspective, infrastructures

tend to remain in the background, and, as such, they only become visible upon breakdown (Star, 1999). However, an important body of research in STS has convincingly argued that infrastructures are more than technological accomplishments (Bowker, Baker, Millerand, & Ribes, 2009; Hughes, 1987; Star & Ruhleder, 1996); they are not just static well-identifiable substrates, but layered and complex amalgams of social, technical and organizational components (Bowker et al., 2009).

The socio-technical view of infrastructures in STS is also usually associated to a relational view of infrastructures, according to which infrastructures become infrastructures in relation to organised practices (Bowker et al., 2009; Star, 1999; Star & Ruhleder, 1996). That is, what is background for one person is a daily object for another, or even a barrier. For instance, whereas a pipe might be an infrastructure for me, ready-to-hand, while I cook at home, it is a topical object for a plumber. And stairs might be infrastructure for someone, but a barrier for wheelchair users. Adopting such practice perspective approach, these authors turn the question 'what is an infrastructure?', to 'when is an infrastructure?' (Star & Ruhleder, 1996). In this regard, the definition of infrastructure becomes a methodological and even epistemological question: as researchers we will need to set the boundaries of the infrastructure in relation to the practices we want to study.

But as Hughes (1987) argues, setting these boundaries, as well as deciding the level of analysis, can be noticeably political. For instance, "an electric light and power system can be so defined that externalities or social costs are excluded from the analysis" (p. 55). Indeed, setting such boundaries is far from self-evident if we consider the entangled nature of infrastructures. Critical towards the layered view of infrastructures, Edwards (1998) argues that there is no linear relationship between an underlying system and the phenomena of the world, as infrastructures might operate on different levels at the same time, and even what is the infrastructure and what is the phenomena remains unclear or inseparable. Infrastructures are not just out there; therefore, as Larkin (2013) puts it, the act of defining an infrastructure can be seen as a categorizing moment, as a political act.

As part of the politics of defining the boundaries of infrastructures, Larkin (2013) draws on several studies in anthropology to show how the visibility of infrastructures

is sometimes mobilized for political purposes, for instance as it can symbolise progress, or it might allow to convince sponsors, even when their functionality sometimes is far from that expected in other contexts. He therefore convincingly argues that instead of assuming that infrastructures remain invisible, in the background, we need to examine how the (in)visibility of infrastructures is mobilized.

Infrastructures are never neutral, or just instrumental, but always world-making; they perform different possible versions of reality and thus they might help sustain some configurations and not others (Carlile, Nicolini, Langley, & Tsoukas, 2013; Introna, 2007; Law, 2002; Mol, 2013; Suchman, 2005). At the same time, they are embedded in relations with other tools, practices, people, and it is through their location in these heterogeneous networks that they help sustain certain orderings.

Based on a relational ontology, what we want to propose is an understanding of infrastructures as simultaneously an accomplishment, and as contributing to constitute the world in specific ways, in a process of mattering taking place within a larger configuration of the world, and as such in constant process of negotiation (Barad 2007). Assuming the relational character of our capacities for action, infrastructures can be seen as part of and participating in the ongoing reconfiguration of objects and subjects, and in the distribution of responsibilities. Thus, orderings can be seen as practices of ontological politics in which subjects and objects are formed as part of assemblages. Accordingly, entities, attributes, responsibilities, are practical accomplishments. Thus, accountability does not refer to relationships between given subjects and objects, but are part of an ontological enactment (Woolgar & Lezaun, 2013, p. 333). As Latour (2003) puts it, once we accept the impossibility of disentangling objects and subjects, technology and society, we realise that matters of fact become states of affairs, in which even defining a computer can lead to bitter disputes. Indeed, defining the boundaries of infrastructures, can be seen as a categorizing moment, a performative and political act with consequences in the definition of responsibilities and accountability.

Making the boundaries of the infrastructure: the case of Uber

Uber has become a taken-for-granted example, and almost a symbol, of the so-called sharing economy, and one of the most recent global and controversial companies to emerge from Silicon Valley. However, Uber's proposition since its inception has been challenged by traditional actors worldwide. Because of Uber's prominence, it has come under scrutiny in the media, in part because of the number of legal cases it is subject to. As a self-styled representative of the "sharing economy", Uber is heavily involved in attempts to redefine the sharing economy and its regulatory regimes. In fact, it has been claimed that Uber has penetrated markets disregarding laws in an attempt to shape these.

Trying to present this case study is challenging as the definition of Uber is highly controversial. The English Wikipedia offers the following definition: "Uber Technologies Inc. is an American technology company headquartered in San Francisco, California, United States, operating in 570 cities worldwide. It develops, markets and operates the Uber car transportation and food delivery mobile apps." ('Uber (company)', 2017) This same article, associates Uber to the concept of sharing economy and refers to Uber as "a pioneer in the sharing economy and the changes in industries." The Spanish Wikipedia, instead, defines Uber ('Uber', 2017b) as an international company that offers private transportation to their customers through their software or app. And the German Wikipedia defines Uber as an American company which offers online services in several cities around the world ('Uber', 2017a). As we can already perceive from these definitions, not only the nature of the company is unclear (technology or transport provider). In fact, it is difficult to point to a singular Uber as different Ubers are enacted in different cities. Furthermore, "Uber" is not just a single juridical entity, but a complex network.

Despite the allure of the "sharing economy", critical voices are raising concerns about various negative social effects related to Uber: erosion of worker's rights, issues of liability, unfair competition, to mention only some. In fact, Uber—or various Ubers, we should say—has faced protests and lawsuits in various countries, resulting in different definitions of their responsibilities and conditions to operate. In fact, several countries and cities have limited or banned Uber. The main controversies generated by Uber's business model are mostly related to two issues: on the one hand, it has disrupted a highly-regulated sector—transport—, on the other hand, the Uber's gig economy

model which assumes that Uber drivers are self-employed has been contested. As we will see, in a clear case of ontological politics, the definition of Uber as a digital platform is at the centre of much of these controversies.

Considering the variety of Ubers, we will focus our analysis on Uber in the UK. Specifically, we draw on the UK lawsuits against Uber, as this can allow us to study controversies. In the UK, Uber currently operates legally, with approximately 30,000 drivers in London. However, the legal status of Uber in the UK was questioned due to the way in which ride prices are calculated by the Uber app. More specifically, after protests and pressures from taxi drivers, the transport regulator Transport for London (TfL) brought the case to court. The question was if Uber app, which calculates surge pricing, should be defined as a taximeter or not, as taximeters are a privilege afforded only to black-cab drivers in return for the extensive training they undergo to learn London's streets. The High Court of Justice (October 2015) ruled that the app was not a taximeter, and therefore Uber could operate legally. More specifically, Lord Justice Ouseley ruled that:

“The question for decision in the light of those agreed facts is whether the Uber PHVs [private hire vehicles] are equipped with a taximeter, that is, a device for calculating fares. In my judgment, these PHVs are not equipped with a taximeter as defined by section 11(3). The driver's Smartphone with the Driver's App is not a device for calculating fares by itself or in conjunction with Server 2, and even if it were, the vehicle is not equipped with it.”

“The driver's Smartphone was the primary candidate device for calculating fares. Server 2 receives inputs from the driver's Smartphone, and elsewhere. The results of the calculation are transmitted to the driver and customer via their Uber APPs and to the third party which debits the customer's account. But the Smartphone carries out no calculations; that is not its purpose. The calculation is carried out in fact by Server 2 and wherever it actually does it, it is not in the vehicle.”

“The essence of a taximeter for the purpose of section 11 is that the device must be for the calculation of the fare then to be charged, based on whatever

inputs are appropriate. (...) The Smartphone is not a “thing designed or adapted for a particular functional purpose” namely calculating fares for the PHV; see the Shorter OED. It is not a taximeter. The Smartphone with its Driver’s App may be essential to enabling the calculation to take place but that does not make it a device for calculating fares.”

Through these excerpts, we can see how the meaning of “taximeter” carries important consequences for the stability of the assemblage of which Uber is part. What Uber is and what Uber is allowed to do is sustained by the thin line of separation between a device which calculates and a device for calculation. It is also sustained by the boundaries set around technologies: “taximeters” are seen to be clearly contained within a car, while the boundaries of “the app” have been expanded to consider the servers needed to make the calculations. As we can see, the ontological status of the entities involved is an accomplishment with important normative consequences.

The second lawsuit in the UK against Uber was brought to the Central London Employment Tribunal in October 2016. The Claimants (Uber drivers) complained about Uber’s failure to pay the minimum wage, and failure to provide paid leave. The Respondents (‘Uber’) saw drivers not as Uber’s workers, but as self-employed. The judge ruled that Uber drivers are “workers” entitled to the minimum wage, paid holiday, sick leave and other normal worker entitlements. Once again, the decision affecting this distribution of responsibilities, centred around the definition of Uber. What was at stake in this case is what **is** Uber? Is Uber “just a digital platform”?

The court ruling makes a precise description of the way Uber (as a whole named the “respondents”) operates in London. The juridical entity ‘Uber’ as such does not exist. In London, it is a conglomerate of firms: Uber London Limited (ULL), a UK company that holds the required Private Hire Vehicle (PHV) license to be able to operate in London vehicles for the purposes of booking and arranging travels; Uber Britannia Limited (UBL) manages PHV licenses outside London; and Uber B.V. (UBV), a Dutch company that holds the legal rights to the App and is the parent company of the previous two. We can also consider as part of the general entity ‘Uber’, their servers and software (for allocating bookings to drivers, payment, route discovery, etc.).

The basic process of Uber is as follows: a rider (alternatively called the Customer or the User, depending on the documents) uses the Uber App to make a booking. Uber's software allocates the rider to a driver depending on a number of factors (e.g. proximity to the rider, driver rating, etc.). The driver, unknowing of the destination, has to decide whether to accept or refuse the request, but penalties are incurred if too many declines are registered. Once in the car, the driver is made aware of the route and the Uber's designed route appears on her mobile phone. This route is to be followed by the driver—Evidence presented by the Claimants shows that negative consequences can happen if it is not (e.g. a rider may complain and the driver may not be paid by Uber).

In the introduction of the ruling, Uber is defined as a “smartphone app” through which the enterprise operates. The Respondent defends that Uber is not a transport company, and that they do not exercise any control over the drivers. Drivers are self-employed and Uber helps them grow their business. However, documents analysed in this ruling (contracts, Uber website, internal Uber documents) show an unclear and variable definition of Uber, and the terms of contract with the drivers. Cutting the controversies short, the Judge's ruling was:

“It seems to us that the Respondents' general case and the written terms on which they rely do not correspond with the practical reality. The notion that Uber in London is a mosaic of 30,000 small business linked by a common 'platform' is to our minds faintly ridiculous.”

As we can see, once again the distribution of responsibilities is dependent on boundary setting: what is Uber? What are its boundaries? As just a platform/technology—as just the infrastructure which Uber tries to make visible—it would not have any responsibility for protecting worker's rights. While the ruling offers an elaborate discussion of evidence in favour of the Claimants, the main rationale for the Judge's ruling is: Uber recruits drivers, imposes conditions to drivers (e.g. sort of car), etc.; therefore, Uber is clearly exercising control over the drivers, which contradicts the idea that drivers are independent, self-employed workers. Similarly, another set of reasons refer to how Uber has control over key information (for

instance about the users), the app sets the default route that drivers have to follow, UBV fixes the price, drivers are subject to performance management through a rating system. We can see here a case of algorithmic management, in which the control over workers traditionally exercised by managers is transferred to technology.

This algorithmic management brings to the fore the question of regulation, and the need to look at its imbrication with technology. While under the logic of the “flexible” gig economy, Uber has tried to disrupt a highly regulated sector and push towards deregulation, at the same time Uber algorithms are regulating drivers and even costumers in a non transparent way.

Constituting boundaries, constituting responsibilities

Notions of sharing economy that focus on dis-intermediation, on the ability of digital infrastructures to connect individuals, seem to downplay the power of platform owners in business models such as Uber. The appropriation of the term “sharing economy” by actors in the gig economy such as Uber in ways that depict a sort of communitarian economy, and the dominant understanding of the notion of digital platform is not innocent; it is generative of certain networks of relations.

Uber presented itself as just a “technology” connecting service providers and costumers. Uber thus can be seen as disrupting by trying to break some networks (drivers as individual independent workers, just linked to the technological platform), while keeping very strong connections to other actors: we are referring to venture capital, which is what sustains an otherwise unviable business.

From the illustrations on the legal controversies of Uber in the UK discussed in this paper, we can see that the definition of the boundaries of the “digital platform” are very much at stake. Uber as a digital platform, as the Respondent in the ruling case discussed would like to have it, suggests a distribution of responsibilities that corresponds to the neoliberal model of the gig economy, in which the “flexible” worker, the “self-employed” can grow their business through the platform.

The visibility and the definition of the borders of the digital platform can be seen indeed as a political act. Such ontological politics are not only taking place in the courts, in the streets where Uber operates. They also take place in the academia. While the layered modular digital platform sustaining multisided markets, talks about generativity, approaching Uber's digital platform from the lens of infrastructures suggests instead a concept of degenerativity, where worker's rights and freedoms are being challenged, and need to be fought back; degenerative of its own project, in light of increasing legal battles that Uber needs to fight in many fronts.

Thinking infrastructures and researching digital platforms

We want to finish with a consideration of the implications of different theorisations of infrastructures for the study of digital platforms in the sharing economy.

1) Infrastructures and digital platforms as clearly defined objects. As substrates.

What is a digital platform?

Much literature has adopted this perspective to study digital platforms as objects with specific architectural characteristics of modularity, etc. In the area of the sharing economy, research has looked into the way digital platforms make matchmaking possible

2) Infrastructures as heterogeneous socio-technical arrangements

How are digital platforms entangled with organisational and social arrangements?

In information systems digital platforms have been studied as techno-organisational concepts; frequently with a focus on platform leaders (i.e. with a focus defined by the object "digital platform")

3) Infrastructure as a relational concept, defined by the practices we want to study

When is infrastructure?

From this perspective digital platforms might only be part of the infrastructures under study. For instance, research still remains to be done that studies the infrastructures of the gig workers' practices.

We could also include here research such as Kornberger et al. (2017) which has studied more specific aspects such as the evaluative infrastructures of accounting practices that help sustain platform organisations.

4) Infrastructures and digital platforms as an accomplishment, as a doing

In this paper we have argued that constituting the boundaries of infrastructures is political and performative, that is, it is implicated in ontological politics, with consequences in the distribution of responsibilities (Latour, 2003; Mol, 2013; Woolgar & Lezaun, 2013). We have proposed a diffractive reading (Haraway, 1992; Barad, 2007) of the digital platforms of the sharing economy to investigate the material-discursive production of digital platforms and their participation in the reconfiguring of the world (Barad 2007).

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